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Phd Research & Study on Economic Growth & Education

Autho'r Details:

Iqbal Shaukat

Affiliation: Financial management Association-Chartered management Association

Email: professionalstudent1000@gmail.com.

Abstract

Economic development is a continuous process.it is not possible in one years,it takes the many years,the impact of economic development is very long.Economic development is the right example of revolution.Economic development is the very integreal part of country human life.Some countries are symbol of Economic development.All the nation should fellow the path way of development..Many countries are the examples for other world.Deregulation,cottage industry,Micro finance, Motivation economic and management policies.Such economy got the destination of Economic development with steadily and smoothly.for example in china and India and Japan have the economic growth target of two percentage,through this way they achieved the economic growth and Development. Economics education is very important for every nation.in the case of economic education we can get the good status in the socitey Economics is the back bone of every country and socitey.Economics system provide the way how to get the goal of devlopment.With the help of economics we can get the consumer price index.Economic data provide information regarding the national income and percapita income.The benefit of economic study we can prove more benefical for the socitey.Economic education provide the way how the all sectors can be devloped.Economics data provide the information regarding the difficulties of nation

Key words: *Economic, education Development, growth, education*

Purpose of research.

I completed my PhD research on economics with great ambition and desire for the business consultant and students and managers and researcher.

Introduction

Economic growth is not roses way,it can be achieved through sacrifices and control on monetary expansion.Economic development is the dream of entire nation.All the nation,s of the world have desire of economic development.Economic development is only way which give the nation how to spend the prosperous life.Economic development is very ken for every nation.Some devloped nation was backward before some decade's,but due to some good economic strategy they achieved the goal of economic development.Japan faced economic disaster after the second world,because of economic growth strategy they started the journey of devlopment,Japan provide the professional and technically education to entire population.They adopted the good management techniques which help the Japan the started the economic growth.In the few years they avhieved the highest growth of economic development.{1-10}

Literature review.

Japan economic model was one explanatory model {for entire region. Japan have the main share in Automobile and in the electric industry. China is one of great example of Economic growth and Development. They organized their economy very well. They organized all the sectors of economy Agriculture, industry, Small medium exchange industry. China started the capital projects like dams and industrial estates. China government announced the policy of deregulation, the policy of deregulation was very attractive for the foreign investment. {2-10}

Chinese governments announced many incentives for foreign investors, as a result of this policy of deregulation the Chinese economy achieved the highest growth of economic development. In the recent Chinese government adopted such foreign policies specially relationship with other countries they achieved the confidence of foreign investors. Bangladesh was the least developed countries of the world, before the some years they design the Economic policies which was very beneficial for the entire population. Bangladesh achieved the highest growth in textile sector and became the main exporter of textile product. In Bangladesh they introduced and implemented the micro finance schemes for cottage base industry. In most recent years they achieved highest rate of economic growth. Vietnam faced the economic disaster before some decades, Vietnam organized the human resource and organized the cottage industries, which create the many employment opportunities. The factor of economic development is that increase in industrialization, {1-10}

Economics education is very vital for every society. Economics education are teaching approximately are taught in every university of world. It is the need of hour that we should get the economics education. Economics education can bring the social revolution in any society. With the help of good economic system we can bring the financial discipline in our society. Financial institutes are the back bone of economy. Qualified economists run the system very well. Economist is the only person which can bring the social revolution in the society. {2-10}

Research regarding the economics growth with qualitative and quantitative perspective.

I conducted the research regarding the importance of economics growth. I prepared the questionnaire regarding the importance of economic growth.

I talked with different categories regarding the importance of economic growth.

The results as follows.

Table:

Categories. Yes no.

Business. 2. 0

Student. 8. 2

Teacher. 10. 1

Economist. 4. 0

Tax consultant 8 0

Accountant. 5 0

All the audience agree with my hypothesis that economic growth is important for one society as a result of qualitative and quantitative method.

Research methodology regarding the importance economics education with quantitative and qualitative perspective.

I conducted the research regarding the importance of economics education ..I prepared the questionnaire regarding the importance of economic education.

I talked with different categories regarding the importance of economic education.

Table:

Categories. Yes no.

Business. 3. 1

Student. 8. 2

Teacher. 10. 1

Economist. 4. 0

Tax consultant 5. 0

Accountant. 6. 0

All the audience agree with my hypothesis that economic education is important for one society.

Discussion regarding economics development.

These are the main tools which can play the vital role in the development of countries. Some countries are the lesson for the entire world if they work hard with spirits the goal of economic development can be achieved, if countries hire good economic expert they can achieve the goal of economic growth and development. In some countries the political stability is not certain, but in spite of all they achieved the goal of economic development. {2-10} Economics education is very important for every nation. In the case of economic education we can get the good status in the society. Economics is the back bone of every country and society. Economics system provide the way how to get the goal of development. With the help of economics we can get the consumer price index. Economic data provide information regarding the national income and per capita income. {2-6} The benefit of economic study we can prove more beneficial for the society. Economic education provide the way how the all sectors can be developed. Economics data provide the information regarding the difficulties of nation. Economic education provide the method how to control the monetary expansion in the society. With the help of economic education we can measure the development of various sectors. In economic study the research is very important, when we study the economic researches we can get the lesson how the economic development achieved. [1-6] economic education and qualifications we study the various economic models which are implemented in various countries. In various countries they achieved the goal of development and growth with the help of good economic education and qualifications. Economics qualifications are base of every society. Economics is consist on various school of thought. Before some decades the some countries faced depression and inflation, because of good economist and good economic education we came over all economic problems. [2-10]

Conclusion

In various countries where the political stability are very fine. They achieved the goal of Economic development. Some countries got achieved of high target of growth in Agriculture sector for example Nepal, Cambodia, India. Such countries introduced the special reforms in relevant sectors. Economic development possible when all the countries adopt such policies which is according to the spirit of economic and Economic

development. we should consider all the sectors regarding economic development. This is not justified that government provide the incentive to one particular sector. Government should provide the equal opportunity to every sectors. Economic development is the base of every society.

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